
ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT ASSESSMENT OF SOLID WASTE DISPOSAL SITES ALONG RIVER NIGER WATERWAYS FOR AQUATIC POLLUTION OF THE ECOSYSTEM

^{1*}Okolotu Godspower Ikechukwu, ²Tambe Enoheta Besong, ³Udom Enyiekere Apkan, ⁴Okeke Chineze Glory

^{1*}Department of Agricultural Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Delta State University of Science and Technology, P.M.B. 05, Ozoro, Nigeria

²Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology, Faculty of Sciences, Delta State University of Science and Technology, P.M.B.05, Ozoro, Nigeria

³Cross River Basin Development Authorities, Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Agricultural and Bioresource Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542082>

Abstract: *The need for soil and water conservation and management of the ecosystem of the water bodies prior pollution prompt the vitality of this research work. Site locations of the three solid waste disposal sites along the major water body of the study area were obtained through field investigation using appropriate survey procedures. The ecosystem survey within 100 meters distance from the three solid waste disposal sites along the Niger river was conducted to study the impact on chemical conditioning of the aquatic ecosystem with regards to water turbidity, water hydronium concentration, health conditions of organisms, species diversity disruption, temperature variation impact of the wastes, heavy metals, electric conductivity, fish and other aquatic animal frequenting, water taste, smell and odour impact contribution to the health effects were used in derivation of the effects impacted by wastes on the ecosystem. Based on the findings, these wastes are treats to aquatic habitants and the ecosystem. Proferable measures to minimize these negative impacts were proffered to the state, federal and global agencies and others towards protecting these aquatic environments.*

Keywords: *Aquatic Pollution; Environmental Impact Assessment; Solid Waste; Ecosystem; Asaba etc.*

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Aquatic Pollution: Water pollution occurs when harmful substances - often chemicals or microorganisms - contaminate a stream, river, lake, ocean, aquifer, or other body of water, degrading water quality and rendering it toxic to humans or the environment (Denchak, 2023). Agricultural wastes also contribute to aquatic pollution. Health issues like skin rashes and infection, respiratory

infections, and hepatitis can emanate from pollution of coastal waters. Aquatic pollution is a serious problem in Nigeria and it is majorly caused by a variety of sources such as industrial effluent, agricultural runoff, solid waste, and oil spills (Akankali and Elenwo, 2015; Olufunke, 2022; Eriegha *et al.*, 2023). Agriculture is the biggest consumer of global freshwater resources, with farming and livestock production using most of the earth's surface water supplies. It is also a serious water polluter. Around the world, agriculture is the leading cause of water degradation (Denchak, 2023). However, globally, it is estimated that about 60% of the population is dwelling in the coastal environments (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021; Okolotu *et al.*, 2024). This calls for proper management and conservation of our coasts. The Asaba River Niger Waterways are vital for the economic and social activities of the region, supporting transportation, trade, and community livelihoods (Okolotu G.I., 2024).

1.2 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA): Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is a tool used to assess the significant effects of a project or development proposal on the environment (MGS, 2024). Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) is a process undertaken by developers when it is considered that a development proposal may have a significant environmental impact (DAERA, 2024). This research work (EIA) was conducted in the early disposal cycle so that recommendations on the mitigation measures can be proffered a timely remediation. Steps in obtaining an EIA are presented in table below;

Table 1: EIA Steps/Stages

S/N	Stage	What Is Involved
1	Screening	Deciding if an EIA is required
2	Scoping	Deciding what needs to be covered in the assessment and reported in the 'EIA Report'
3	Preparing the EIA Report	The EIA report has to include the likely significant environmental effects of the development
4	Making an application and consultation	The EIA Report and development application must be publicised (including electronic advertisement), interested parties and the public must be given an opportunity to give their views on it
5	Decision making	The EIA Report and any comments made on it must be taken into account by the competent authority before they decide whether to give consent for the development. The decision notice has to be published
6	Post decision	The developer starts any monitoring required by the competent authority

Source: MGS, 2024

The flowchart process of EIA is presented in figure one (1) below;

Figure 1: Flow Diagram of the EIA Process and Parallel Studies (FAO, 2024)

1.3 Solid Waste Disposal: Inadequate disposal of waste, particularly plastic waste, has been documented in all the major ocean basins, beaches, rivers, lakes, and even in remote environments such as the Arctic and Antactical (Sanabria *et al.*, 2023). In many areas, previous researches have existed for environmental and ecosystem management. However, no study has comprehensively assessed waste leakage into aquatic environments from a waste management perspective (Sanabria *et al.*, 2023). Traditional views regarding the release and open dumping cause and exacerbate many

problems and environmental effects (Sajjadi *et al.*, 2017). These wastes are known as municipal solid wastes. MSW contains: Biomass, or biogenic (plant or animal products), materials such as paper, cardboard, food waste, grass clippings, leaves, wood, and leather products, nonbiomass combustible materials such as plastics and other synthetic materials made from petroleum, and noncombustible materials such as glass and metals (EIA, 2024). Proper control and waste management play important roles in improving the quality of the environment and thereby promote public health and wildlife protection (Sajjadi *et al.*, 2017).

Three typical examples of waste disposal sites along waterways are presented in figure two (2) below;

Figure 2: Major Waste Dump Sites along Asaba Niger Waterways (Photograph at the Study Area) These sites are: Site I (Otu – Ogwu area), site II (hinterland area), and site III (cable Marine area).

1.4 Ecosystem: The ecosystem is a unit of connected living and nonliving things as a system. According to BISE, (2024), ecosystems are living systems that cover the entire surface of the earth (land and water). Ecosystem is a combination of two words “ecology” and “system. This is also referred to as ecological system. This is due to the connectivity and dependency of each sectional unit of the system. The water, water temperature, plants, animals, air, light and soil all work together as a

Figure 3: Location Of Study Area And Satellite Map Showing Asaba And Its Section Of Niger River (Okolotu and Oluka, 2021).

Other materials include: 8mp site camera, thermometer, field boat, *etc.*

III. METHODS

Site locations of the three solid waste disposal sites along the study area were achieved through field investigation using appropriate survey procedures. The factors considered are the soil and aquatic ecosystem. The ecosystem survey of 100meters distance from three solid waste disposal sites along the Niger was conducted to study fish and other aquatic animal frequenting. Impact on chemical conditioning of the aquatic ecosystem with regards to water turbidity (using Nephelometric technique), water Hydronium concentration, health conditions of organisms, species diversity disruption (using population), temperature variation (using direct measurements with the LCD portable digital multi – stem thermometer according to Okolotu and Oluka, 2021a), heavy metal (using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry technique), electric conductivity (using Electrometric technique) were recorded and used in derivation of the effects impacted by wastes on the ecosystem. Fish and other aquatic animal frequenting, taste, smell and odour were also assessed for the impact contribution to the health effects from the waste disposal sites.

IV. RESULTS

The results obtained from this research study are presented below;

Table 2: EIA of Ecosystem Parameters

S/N	Impact Type	Parameters	SITE I	Site II	Site III
1	Chemical Impacts	Turbidity (NTU)	0.18	0.09	0.09
2		Water hydronium concentration (Unitless)	5.9	6.4	5.7
3		Species diversity disruption	High	High	High
4		Temperature variation (°C)	32	28	29
5		Electric Conductivity (µs/cm)	0.3	0.02	0.02
6	Heavy metals Impact	Iron (mg/kg)	0.03	0.04	0.04
7		Copper (mg/kg)	0.03	0.08	0.05
8		Lead (mg/kg)	0.02	0.02	0.03
9		Zinc (mg/kg)	0.02	0.01	0.02

10		Mercury (mg/hu)	0.003	0.006	0.008
----	--	-----------------	-------	-------	-------

Taste, smell and odour impact contribute to the health effects from the waste disposal sites. Fish and other aquatic animal frequenting were low within the 100 meters distance.

V. DISCUSSIONS

The impacts of these wastes were higher during wet or rainy season than in dry season. This was due to rainwater triggering the ecosystem environment physically by facilitating there wash in, transportation and leakage upon dissolve. These wastes can be made useful using energy plants. These waste plants are deployable to recycling wastes to a more useful material. New recycling techniques are being developed that might improve recyclability which can result in potential closed loop recycling (Emmerik and Schwarz, 2024). These methods include chemical recycling (by dissolving the plastic in a solvent) and thermochemical recycling (pyrolysis) (Ragaert *et al.*, 2017). According to Deltaway, (2018), waste – to – energy plants reduce 2,000 pounds of garbage to ash that weighs between 300 pounds and 600 pounds, and they reduce the volume of waste by about 87%. This involves use of wastes to fuel a recycling that produces electricity. The burning fuel heats water into steam that drives a turbine to create electricity (Deltaway, 2018). Generating electricity in a mass - burn waste – to - energy plant involves the following processes: dumping of waste from garbage trucks into a large pit, transferring the large wastes by grabbing and dumping it into a combustion chamber, burning the waste as fuel to release heat capable of turning water into steam in a boiler, providing high - pressure steam which turns the blades of the turbine generator to produce electricity, removing pollutants from the combustion gas using the air pollution control system before the gas is released through a smoke stack, and collection of the Ash from the boiler and the air - pollution control system. These steps can be seen in figure four (4) below;

Figure 4: Waste Disposal system (Deltaway, 2018)

Comparably with advance disposal methods like in figure four (4) above, and the current disposal methods of the waste presented in site I of figure two (2) above, the bounded wastes disposable will be more effectively disposed using the advance methods. Governments are being urged to implement and enforce policies and laws at the national and river basin level to sustainably manage freshwater ecosystems, balancing the needs of communities, businesses, and the environment (UNW, 2024).

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, these wastes are treat to aquatic habitants. The study area and other relatives places in Delta State, Nigeria and global need the advance waste disposal systems. Proferable measures to minimize these negative impacts should be deployed by state or federal environmental agencies to help these coastal dwellers protect their aquatic environments.

Authors Contribution

Okolotu Godspower Ikechukwu ^{PhD} (Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Validation, Writing – original draft, *etc*); Tambe Enoheta Besong ^{PhD} (Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, *etc*); Udom Enyiekere Apkan ^{PhD} (Visualization, Investigation, *etc*); Okeke Chineze Glory ^{PhD} (Resources, Writing – review & editing, *etc*).

References

- BISE, 2024. Ecosystems and their services. Biodiversity Information System for Europe. P 1. <https://biodiversity.europa.eu/europes-biodiversity/ecosystems>
- DAERA, 2024. Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). Department Of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affair. P 1. <https://daera-ni.gov.uk/articles/environmental-impact-assessment-eia>
- EIA, 2024. Waste – To – Energy (Municipal Solid Waste). U.S Energy Information Administration. P 1. <https://eia.gov/energyexplained/biomass/waste-to-energy.php>
- Emmerik T.V., And Schwarz A., 2024. Plastic Debris in Rivers. WIREs Water. Volume 7, Issue 1. P 12. <https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/wat2.1398>
- FAO, 2024. EIA Process. Chapter 3. Food and Agriculture Organization. P 4. <https://fao.org/4/V8350E/v8350e06.htm>
- MGS, 2024. Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Overview. My Government Scotland. P 2. <https://mygov.scot/eia>

Scientific and Engineering Letters

Volume 13 Issue 4, October-December 2025

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 7.72

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/letters>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

- NHPB, 2024. Ecosystem. Nature Works of New Hampshire Public Broadcasting. P 1 & 3. <https://nhpbs.org/natureworks/nwepecosystems.htm>
- Okolotu G.I., 2024. Shear Stress Impact On Coastal Water Defense Structures in Asaba River Niger Waterways. Tuijin Jishu/Journal Of Propulsion Technology. Volume 45. Number 3. P 2. <https://propulsionejournal.com/index.php/journal/article/view/7718>
- Okolotu G.I., Nwadiolu R., Akwenuke O.M., Adaigho D.O., and Udom E.A., 2024. Measurement and Computation of Sea Level Depth for the Evaluation of the Effect of Global Water Rising. Journal of Data Acquisition and Processing. 39 (1). P 1110. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.755105>
- Sanabria A.G., Lindi F., And Greenwell B., 2024. Drowning In Waste: Pollution Hotspots in Aquatic. International Institute for Applied System Analysis. P 2. <https://iiasa.ac.at/news/jun-2024/drowning-in-waste-pollution-hotspots-in-aquatic-environments>
- UNW, 2024. Water and Ecosystems. United Nations Water. P 4. <https://unwater.org/water-facts/water-and-ecosystems>
- Denchak M., 2023. Water Pollution: Everything You Need to Know. Natural Resources Defense Council. P 1. <https://nrdc.org/stories/water-pollution-everything-you-need-know#whatis>
- Eriegha O.J., Eyo V.O., and Adeleke I.A., 2023 Influence of Crude Oil Exposure and Recovery on Growth Performance of Oreochromis Niloticus. Proc. Of The Maiden Inter. Conf. Of Safnr, Oaustech. P 54. https://researchgate.net/publication/376272821_INFLUENCE_OF_CRUDE_OIL_EXPOSURE_AND_RECOVERY_ON_GROWTH_PERFORMANCE_OF_Oreochromis_niloticus#fullTextFileContent
- Olufunke, K. A. (2022). Water Pollution in Nigeria and Its Effect on Agriculture: A Case Study of Niger Delta. Research and Science Today Journal. Volume 1, No. 23. P 3. <https://doi:10.38173/RST.2022.23.1.2:21-31>
- Akankali, J. A., and Elenwo, E. I. (2015). Sources of Marine Pollution on Nigerian Coastal Resources: An Overview. Open Journal of Marine Science. Volume 5. Number 02. P 226. <https://doi:10.4236/ojms.2015.52018>

Scientific and Engineering Letters

Volume 13 Issue 4, October-December 2025

ISSN: 2836-9483

Impact Factor: 7.72

Journal Homepage: <https://americaserial.com/Journals/index.php/letters>

Email: contact@americaserial.com

Official Journal of America Serial Publication

Okolotu G.I., And Oluka S.I., 2021. Determination Of The Impacts Of Wave Attributes On Coastline Erosion. *International Research Journal Of Applied Sciences, Engineering And Technology*. Volume 7. Number 5. P 8. www.cird.online/IRJASET

Okolotu, G. I., and Oluka, S. I., 2021. Shore Reclamation for Agricultural Use, a Combat to Shoreline Erosion. *Advance Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6(5), P 4 & 14. <https://aspjournals.org/ajset/index.php/ajset/article/view/28>

UNEP, 2021. A beginner's Guide to Ecosystem Restoration. UN Environment Program. P 1. <https://unep.org/news-and-stories/story/beginners-guide-ecosystem-restoration>

Deltaway, 2018. Waste to Energy. P 1. <https://deltawayenergy.com/2018/08/waste-to-energy-how-itworks/4> and <https://ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5410896/#b13-epj-09-3714>

Ragaert, K., Delva, L., & Geem, V.K., 2017. Mechanical and Chemical Recycling Of Solid Plastic Waste. *Waste Management. Web of Science*. 69, P 26. <https://doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.044>.

Sajjadi S.A., Aliakbari Z., Matlabi M., Biglari H., and Rasouli S.S., 2017. Environmental Impact Assessment of Gonabad Municipal Waste Landfill Site Using Leopold Matrix. *National Center for Biotechnology Information. Electron Physician*. Volume 9. Issue 2. P 3716. <https://doi.org/10.19082/3714>